

Research Report

**Medical Planning for Expedition to Mountain Huayna
Potosi**

By: Abu S Galib

Diploma in Remote and Offshore Medicine

Module C08: Trauma and Medical Emergencies

The Royal College of Surgeons of Edinburgh

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Background¹

An expedition society plans a 6-week trip to the mountain Huayna Potosi (6008 m), located in the Central Andes (Cordillera Real subrange), in northwestern Bolivia. The team will consist of 15 adults. Along with climbing the mountain, there will be sightseeing activity at Santa Cruz (400 m), situated in the Central Bolivia lowlands. Both, El Alto (4150 m), which is the nearest city to the mountain, and Santa Cruz are accessible by air. Alternative routes are available via La Paz (3650 m), the capital of Bolivia, and near to El Alto. The team is scheduled to leave the Heathrow Airport (LHR; 25 m) for La Paz on 4th July, 2023. After a period of acclimatization in La Paz, the team will resume excursion towards Huayna Potosi.

1. Hazard identification and risk assessment.

1.1 Geomorphological and Climatic Hazards (Huayna Potosi)².

Geomorphological features consist of sheet ice, rock formations, crevasses. Snow on ground may be loose and deep. Vertical ice and rock formations may be found enroute to the summit.

Climatic features (above 2500 meters), consist of low atmospheric pressure, low oxygen concentration and low temperature. Rainy season starts in November and ends in March³.

1.2 Bolivia⁴.

Socioeconomic: Poverty level remains high for large part of the population, and access to basic services like health, education and housing is severely limited.

Geomorphological: Bolivia lies in an active volcanic and tectonic belt, but related events, have not produced widespread loss of life or property. Most of the terrain is above 2500 meters.

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Climatic: The effect of hydrometeorological events is more widespread, with severe loss and damage caused by floods, landslides, droughts and frost. Both high and lowlands are affected.

1.3 Area around Santa Cruz⁵

Hazardous zones prone to water pollution, wildfires, drought, and floods have been identified in the valleys supporting the city.

1.4 Medical Facilities⁶

- Public health services in Bolivia, remain crowded, and are often inaccessible to foreigners.
- A list of private medical facilities is available on gov.uk website. Specific link is provided in the Predeparture preparation chart. For this trip, it is required to have medical insurance that covers expenses at designated facilities, and for emergency evacuation to the nearest healthcare facility, and repatriation, if situation so demands.
- There is no reliable ambulance service.
- Medical standards are below par in mountainous regions, and better in and around Santa Cruz, and in metropolitan areas.

1.5 Risk assessment chart (Expedition Huayna Potosi, Bolivia 2023).

Hazards	Risks	Injury pattern/disease type	Likelihood
Mountain Huayna Potosi			

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<p>Geomorphological⁷: Sheet ice, rockslides, vertical rock and ice formations, Icefall, crevasses, avalanche, loose and deep snow, natural dam outburst. UV radiation.</p>	<p>Slips, fall from height, entrapment in hidden crevasses or under avalanche, hit by falling rocks, swept by flash floods⁸.</p>	<p>Blunt and sharp trauma to any part of the body, dehydration, asphyxiation, snow blindness, sunburn.</p>	<p>High</p>
<p>Climatic³ (Climbing season, April to October- November): Low atmospheric pressure, low oxygen concentration, precipitation below 200 mm on most days. Daytime temperature, hovers around +7 degrees centigrade and night time temperature may fall to -8 degrees. On cold nights temperature can drop</p>	<p>Physiological decompensation, low visibility,</p>	<p>High Altitude Headache, Acute Mountain Sickness, High Altitude Pulmonary and Cerebral Oedema, cold injury, Hypothermia, frostbite. Fatigue and dehydration. Snow blindness</p>	<p>High</p>

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to -12 degrees. Occasional high winds.			
Bolivia: Lowlands			
Geomorphological: Unstable land formations, erosion, floods, wildfire, water pollution, landslides	Drowning, entrapment	Asphyxiation, burn injury	Moderate
Endemic diseases ⁹	Yellow fever, Leishmaniasis, American Trypanosomiasis, Malaria, Typhoid, Hepatitis A and B, Rabies, Dengue, Chikungunya, Zika, Hantavirus.	Primary and secondary effects.	Low to moderate
Feedback from team members A			
Feedback from team members B			

2. Predeparture preparation¹⁰.

Section	Details	Advisory	Further information
Clientele briefing regarding hazards and risks	As per section 1.	Refer to hazards and risk assessment chart	Consult bibliography at the end of this paper.
Medical Screening and dental checkup ¹¹ .	Chief Medic to collect personal medical dossiers from the society medical office;	At least 90 days before departure, all team members, including medics, must submit to the society medical office: information and informed consent/full medical history and examination certificate/ECG/CBC/Exercise stress test (if >50yrs)/Urine dipstick/blood sugar/Blood group and Rh; screening for viral and treponemal pathogens/Transaminase/Gamma-GT/Creatinine/CDT/Beta-HCG (if pre-menopause)/Stool OPC (if cooking)/dental examination(recommended)/gynec	Consult your GP; also submit your GP and specialist details to the society medical office. A donor-recipient chart based on blood test results will be created, in case, the need for blood transfusion arises.

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		<p>ological certificate(recommended)/ filled health questionnaire/evidence of insurance cover.</p>	
<p>Immunization requirements¹²</p>	<p>Up to date routine vaccination schedule as per UK regulations;</p>	<p>Required: Yellow Fever, Covid-19. Recommended: Hepatitis A and B, Tetanus, Typhoid, Rabies, BCG. See Section 5, Further notes below.</p>	<p>https://www.gov.uk/for-eign-travel-advice/bolivia/health. After going through the above website, discuss with your GP, and carry proof of vaccination.</p>
<p>Other conditions; Prophylactics</p>	<p>Malaria; Dengue; Leishmaniasis; Antimalarials</p>	<p>Malaria transmission risks remain in certain lowlands; starting chemoprophylaxis before departure is recommended.</p>	<p>Discuss options with your GP. All medicines should be accompanied by a valid prescription.</p>
<p>First Aid Training</p>	<p>Advisable, that at least two team members get trained in basic first</p>	<p>Components: Assess Scene Safety/Safe approach/Basic Life Support/Hemorrhage control/Fracture management/Unconscious</p>	<p>Saint John Ambulance, or British Red Cross. https://www.rgs.org/in-the-field/</p>

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	aid, to aid the chief medic.	patient/ Moving the injured team member.	https://www.rgs.org/in-the-field/advice-training/
Health and hygiene education	Follow general standards.	Avoid drinking water that is not marked safe/Avoid tick and mosquito bites in lowlands.	Camp health and hygiene regulations will be provided on arrival at base camp.
Medical kit management	The approved list of items, will be procured from authorized distributors in UK, and will be shipped to La Paz. One member of the medical team will receive the item at the airport. Supporting documentation, including a letter from a medical authority will be sent along with.		
Healthcare access at destination	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • As per section 4. • List of medical practitioners and clinics in Bolivia (Link)¹³. • For insurance (Link)¹⁴. 		
Medic/s ¹⁵	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Proof of theoretical and practical technical mountain training. (Climbing, basic rescue maneuvers, patient transport). • Proof of professional indemnity. • Medical qualification and experience documents. 		

3.1 List of essential medical items¹⁶.

Range	Item
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<p>Equipment: Diagnostic</p>	<p>Stethoscope, Aneroid BP instrument, Otoscope and Ophthalmoscope, Glucometer, Bag-mask valve apparatus, Handheld Suction Unit, Laryngoscope; Video laryngoscope, oximeter, head torch, pen torch, thermometer, portable ultrasound.</p>
<p>Equipment; High Altitude and rescue</p>	<p>EmOx, Portable Hyperbaric chamber, Kendrick's, Floating stretcher, partial rebreathing mask and tubing, Hudson's mask, nebulizer mask. Portable oxygen cylinders (2.5-3 L size; capacity 800-1200 liters); 4 each for each team member, including medics. Extra cylinders for medical team, in case of rescue scenario.</p>
<p>Equipment; Trauma and Others</p>	<p>Trauma shears, first aid scissors, blunt and toothed forceps,</p>
<p>Consumables</p>	<p>Hard Cervical Collar; Adult, lancets, glucose testing strips, Endotracheal tubes, LMA, ET bougie, Nasopharyngeal Airway, Guedel airway; Tracheostomy set, Catheter mounts, nasogastric tube, safety pins, urine pregnancy kit, Sharps box, spacer device, nebulizer, Ambu bag</p>
<p>Consumables; Trauma, Wounds, etc</p>	<p>Bladder Syringe, Catheter set, Blizzard blanket, Chest drain set, burn kit, combat application tourniquet, Celox granules, scalpels, suturing set, Pads (Various; gauge/eye/abdominal/Vaseline/etc.), gloves, suturing kit, Heimlich's, SAM splints, Urine pregnancy kit, Swabs (alcohol/povidone/cetrimide/insect bite/etc.), Bandages (Various; Elastic/triangular/adhesive/gauge/hypoallergenic/silk/ZnO/Steristrips/Cling wrap/Crepe/waterproof/Tubigrip/etc.),</p>

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Medications (formulations; various)	Paracetamol, Diclofenac, Ibuprofen, Codeine, Tramadol, Morphine, Antimicrobials (extended range; various), antimalarials, antifungals, prednisolone, antacids, famotidine, hyoscine, ORS, bisacodyl, glucose, loperamide tab (1000), domperidone tab (100), domperidone suppositories (10), Sterculia sachets (40) , omeprazole, ondansetron, prochlorperazine, antihypertensives, inhalers, chlorpheniramine, otrivin, salbutamol, Povidone-iodine, surgical spirit, cefrimide, Tranexamic acid, dental cement.
Vaccines; immunoglobulins	Tetanus, Rabies, Scorpion, Anti Snake Venom Serum.
Local anesthetics	Bupivacaine, Xylocaine,
Emergency	GTN, atropine, adrenaline, ketamine, lorazepam, midazolam, dexamethasone, hydrocortisone, nifedipine MR, dental first aid kit,
Topical; Others	Acyclovir, aqueous, clotrimazole, hemorrhoidal, mupirocin, Painkiller, Eye and ear drops (Various), dimetindene, silver nitrate.
Injection equipment; Others	Syringes/needles/insulin syringe/IV set/IV cannula/
IV fluids	Normal Saline (1000 ml; 20)/Ringer Lactate (1000 ml; 10)/Glucose 5% (500ml; 10); Hypertonic Saline 3% (500 ml; 10)/ Haemaccel/Gelofusine(1000 ml; 20)
Communication	Desktop PC with internet access (Base Camp only). Satellite phone, strobes, flairs,

<p>Challenges in the mountain environment¹⁷</p>	<p>All items need to be resilient for proper functioning at high altitude, and cold environments. It is preferable to select items that have a field history in similar or harsher conditions. Adhesive bandages and similar items may not work in cold mountainous areas. The expedition, is also an opportunity to field test all items and record a performance log. Special attention needs to be given to electronic devices.</p>
<p>Principles¹⁸</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Field tested items preferable, or those used extensively in prehospital settings. 2. Packed, labelled, documented, and authorization letter from a licensed medical practitioner. 3. Familiar to expedition medics, who must be appropriately qualified. 4. Expedition medics to assemble and test all equipment, before packing. 5. Medic must contact local embassy in Bolivia, to establish a logistical chain, if resupply is required. 6. Medic to establish satellite phone communication beforehand, with GP and medical consultants, both in Bolivia and in United Kingdom, if advice is required during expedition.

4. Policy for accessing healthcare and medical supply while in Bolivia.

Individual healthcare:

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- A standard personal medical kit will be issued to all team members, on arrival at the hotel in La Paz. This kit is to be used for basic first aid purposes and for common ailments, as per the instruction leaflet provided. Additional injectable preparations for high altitude illness will also be provided.
- 2 high pressure emergency oxygen cylinders will be provided for each team member
- All team members must have travel insurance covering treatment at local facilities and for emergency evacuation. Local private clinics often have agreements with international insurance companies. For details contact your insurance provider or British Mountaineering Council. All treatment has to be paid for.
- At least 8 weeks before trip check country specific advice available on National Travel Health Network and Centre on TravelHealthPro website. Information is also available from NHS(Scotland) on the website FitForTravel.
- Bolivia regulations may consider some medications as controlled substances or narcotics, which are considered over the counter or regular medications in other countries. Some prescription medicines may be considered illegal. For any medications being carried along, check with embassy in Bolivia, for the legal status.
- For all personal medications, being carried along, it is advisable to carry prescription/s from a licensed medical practitioner of your home country, to prevent any hassles at the customs or with other authorities. The prescription/s should describe the medical condition/s, and use generic names, instead of brand names.
- Medical shops (Farmacia), are found in major metropolitan areas. Many medications are provided, without a prescription, but it is advisable to get a prescription from a local clinic.

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- There are chances of buying substandard or counterfeit medical items; to be safe, bring all personal medications to last at least 2 weeks longer than the trip.

5. Process to deal with accidental death within the group, while at altitude¹⁹.

Once a likely death has occurred at altitude:

- a. All activities to be ceased by the Expedition Leader. Medical Officer (MO) to ensure scene safety and prevent further injuries to other members.
- b. Members to attempt, retrieval of body, without undue risk.
- c. MO to file incident report form, after investigation, and gathering information from witnesses. Signature from at least one witness to be registered. Entry to be made in logbook of events. Local police to be notified, via base camp.
- d. If body retrieval is possible, packaging and transport to the base camp and then to the nearest state hospital to be arranged.

Once death is confirmed at the State Hospital, the following further steps will be taken:

- a. The expedition head office located in United Kingdom, to be informed. The general condition of the other team members, will also be conveyed.
- b. Two persons from headquarters, will meet the family members of the deceased, to convey news of death, in person. The family members will be provided access to all support services, immediately. In some cases, police in the home country will convey the news.
- c. Local embassy of the deceased, will be informed. Full details regarding incident will be conveyed. Embassies of other team members, will also be notified regarding wellbeing of the members.

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- d. A police report will be procured, and an autopsy if indicated, will be carried out.
- e. Insurance companies, will be contacted. The incident report, with additional inputs from the expedition leader, to be forwarded to the company, and contacts will be established between the company and local authorities for the purpose of repatriation.

Repatriation steps:

- a. The local embassy, transport companies, and country authorities will be contacted.
- b. Entry in the event logbook will include details, regarding time, place and person, along with negotiation outcome.
- c. Insurance company, in conjunction with other entities will arrange for repatriation.

Others:

- a. A written press release will be issued.
- b. Attention to the needs of the team members and local support staff, will be given.
- c. A supervised and approved communication channel will be established, between team members and their families back home.
- d. After the expedition, follow up counselling and monitoring of team members will be recommended.

5. Further notes

5.1 Oxygen cylinders:

- To be used for one to two hours, if you have HAI, and then during sleep at 1-2 l/min.

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- Test all cylinders personally before departure and after arrival at base camp.

5.2 Portable Oxygen concentrators (POC)²⁰:

- These devices will be used to enrich oxygen concentration at base camp.
- The medical team may decide to use them to treat cases at base camp²¹.
- An electrical power source will be necessary; chances of equipment failure cannot be ruled out.
- Currently there is no case studies or large trials regarding POC use while climbing.

5.3 Vaccination and other requirements²²:

- Yellow Fever-Required for anyone, who will be travelling from a country with risk of transmission, and greater than one year in age (UK is not on the list). Recommended for all travellers, who will be visiting areas with less than 2300 meters height.
- Rabies-Endemic regions found. Vaccines and immunoglobulins may not be available. Recommended for all travellers.
- Covid-19-Required for all travellers. Alternatively, a negative result of RT-PCR or rapid antigen test produced within a stipulated time period may be acceptable.
- Hepatitis A-Recommended for all travellers. Alternatively, the immunoglobulin gives protection for 2 months.
- Hepatitis B-Recommended for all travellers, as this disease carries a high risk of mortality and morbidity, including hepatocellular carcinoma.
- Typhoid-Recommended for all travellers, who will visit lowlands of potential endemicity.
- Required- Up to date routine vaccinations for all adults including: Chickenpox, Diphtheria, Pertussis, Tetanus, Mumps, Measles, Rubella, Flu, Polio, Shingles.

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- Malaria-Endemic in lowlands. Start chemoprophylaxis up to 2 weeks earlier, after consulting your GP.
- Fluids
 - A. Haemaccel/Gelofusine: Safe for use, when thawed after being frozen. Indications- haemorrhagic blood loss.
 - B. Normal Saline: Indications-Volume expansion,
 - C. Hypertonic Saline: Indicated for small volume resuscitation, at high altitude regions.
 - D. Delivery-rewarmed fluids will be delivered via insulated bottles/bags and tubing sets.

Bibliography

1. Cheng EK. Is high-altitude mountaineering Russian roulette? *J Quant Anal Sports*. 2013;9(1):1-14. doi:10.1515/jqas-2012-0038
2. Kalvoda J, Rosenfeld CL. *Geomorphological Hazards in High Mountain Areas*. Springer Science & Business Media; 2012.
3. Simulated historical climate & weather data for Cerro Huayna Potosi. meteoblue. Accessed November 13, 2022. https://www.meteoblue.com/en/weather/historyclimate/climatemodelled/cerro-huayna-potosi_bolivia_3914607
4. 1943.pdf. Accessed November 5, 2022. <https://cdn.odi.org/media/documents/1943.pdf>
5. Cantini F, Castelli G, Foderi C, et al. Evidence-Based Integrated Analysis of Environmental Hazards in Southern Bolivia. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. 2019;16(12):2107. doi:10.3390/ijerph16122107
6. Health_System_Profile-Bolivia_2007.pdf. Accessed November 8, 2022. https://www.paho.org/hq/dmdocuments/2010/Health_System_Profile-Bolivia_2007.pdf
7. Huayna Potosi .:Bolivian Mountain Guides:. Accessed November 13, 2022. <https://www.bolivianmountainguides.com/huayna-potosi.php>
8. Crust L. Personality and mountaineering: A critical review and directions for future research. *Personal Individ Differ*. 2020;163:110073. doi:10.1016/j.paid.2020.110073
9. Moya Quiroga Gomez V, Kure S, Udo K, Mano A. Analysis of exposure to vector-borne diseases due to flood duration, for a more complete flood hazard assessment: Llanos de Moxos, Bolivia. *Ribagua*. 2018;5(1):48-62. doi:10.1080/23863781.2017.1332816
10. Houge Mackenzie S, Kerr JH. A (mis)guided adventure tourism experience: An autoethnographic analysis of mountaineering in Bolivia. *J Sport Tour*. 2012;17(2):125-144. doi:10.1080/14775085.2012.729901
11. Mieske K, Flaherty G, O'Brien T. Journeys to High Altitude—Risks and Recommendations for Travelers with Preexisting Medical Conditions. *J Travel Med*. 2010;17(1):48-62. doi:10.1111/j.1708-8305.2009.00369.x
12. NaTHNaC - Bolivia. Accessed December 3, 2022. <https://travelhealthpro.org.uk/country/30/bolivia>
13. Bolivia: medical facilities and practitioners. GOV.UK. Accessed November 7, 2022. <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/bolivia-medical-facilities-and-practitioners>
14. BMC Insurance. Accessed December 10, 2022. <https://www.thebmc.co.uk/modules/insurance/>

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15. 20111027-MED Consensus Guidelines on Mountain Emergency Medicine and Risk Reduction.pdf. Accessed November 12, 2022. <https://www.alpine-rescue.org/system/production/article/documents/file/000/187/80e533fd954fedd5a67b8573fb059f3e7eedef448cd6c1d4dd8c4f6d779be908/20111027-MED%20Consensus%20Guidelines%20on%20Mountain%20Emergency%20Medicine%20and%20Risk%20Reduction.pdf?1651603835>
16. Faculty of Prehospital Care, Royal College of Surgeons Edinburgh guidance for medical provision for wilderness medicine | Extreme Physiology & Medicine | Full Text. Accessed November 5, 2022. <https://extremephysiolmed.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s13728-015-0041-x>
17. Hindle EM, Henning JD. Critical care at extremes of temperature: effects on patients, staff and equipment. *BMJ Mil Health*. 2014;160(4):279-285. doi:10.1136/jramc-2013-000076
18. Iserson KV. Medical Planning for Extended Remote Expeditions. *Wilderness Environ Med*. 2013;24(4):366-377. doi:10.1016/j.wem.2013.05.005
19. Firth PG, Zheng H, Windsor JS, et al. Mortality on Mount Everest, 1921-2006: descriptive study. *BMJ*. 2008;337:a2654. doi:10.1136/bmj.a2654
20. Inogen, Inc. Inogen, Inc. Accessed December 7, 2022. <https://provider.inogen.com/en>
21. Litch JA, Bishop RA. Oxygen concentrators for the delivery of supplemental oxygen in remote high-altitude areas. *Wilderness Environ Med*. 2000;11(3):189-191. doi:10.1580/1080-6032(2000)011[0189:OCFTDO]2.3.CO;2
22. Bolivia - Traveler view | Travelers' Health | CDC. Accessed November 5, 2022. https://wwwnc.cdc.gov/travel/destinations/traveler/none/bolivia?s_cid=ncezid-dgmq-travel-single-001